

Nature-based mitigation strategies to sea level rise and other climate change impacts on the Sundarbans Mangrove of Bangladesh: Analyzing the legal, institutional and policy framework

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Abstract

The overarching objective of the study was to offer suitable nature-based mitigation strategies to cope with the adverse effects of sea level rise and other impacts on the Sundarbans Mangrove, the largest single block of tidal halophytic mangrove forest in the world, based on stakeholders' perceptions. The study also attempted to identify the bottlenecks of the existing legal, policy, and institutional frameworks in this regard. The study revealed that the accumulation of river sediments can counter sea level rise in Bangladesh. On the other hand, stopping brackish shrimp culture can control the pace of salinization, biological invasion and alteration in the vegetation composition of this mangrove. Facilitating natural regeneration and the natural succession of native tree species can minimize the damage caused by tropical cyclones. It was found that there is no specific law or public policy which can effectively support nature-based solutions. Instead, many fragmented laws and policies created jurisdictional overlapping, followed by interest conflicts in most cases. The study recommends legal and institutional reforms to abolish jurisdictional overlapping and establish effective climate governance.

Keywords: Climate change, Sundarbans mangrove, nature-based mitigation, sea level rise, institutional framework, policy and legal framework

Introduction

The Sundarbans Delta in Bangladesh is experiencing both predictable and unpredictable climate change impacts every year (Khan 2019, Chowdhury *et al.* 2020; Haque *et al.* 2020; Ali *et al.* 2019; Hasnat *et al.* 2020; Chiba *et al.* 2017; Alam *et al.* 2020; Billah 2018; Dastagir 2015; Rahman 2020; Rahman 2021; Rahman *et al.* 2021, Rahman 2022 a, b). Sea level rise, increased salinity and frequent tropical cyclones have become very familiar to the community (Rahman 2023 a, b, c, d, e). Most of the rivers of Bangladesh flow from north to south, silting up the mangrove delta and draining into the Bay of Bengal. The mangrove is a transitional territory between the freshwater rivers originating from the Ganges and the Bay of Bengal. Climate change poses a high risk to the ecosystems and landmass of this delta. The major threats are high levels of salinity, sedimentation, cyclones, storm surges, water logging and land erosion (Kaiser 2023).

Figure 1: Climate change impacts on the Sundarbans Mangrove of Bangladesh

The overarching objective of the study was to offer suitable nature-based mitigation strategies to cope with the adverse effects of sea level rise and other impacts on the Sundarbans Mangrove, the largest single block of tidal halophytic mangrove forest in the world, based on stakeholders' perceptions. The study also attempted to identify the bottlenecks of the existing legal, policy, and institutional frameworks to sea level rise and other climate change impacts on the Sundarbans Mangrove of Bangladesh. Based on respondents' perceptions, a mitigation strategy was developed.

Methodology

Figure 2: Methodological framework

The study is qualitative and empirical data was used. A total number of 60 respondents were personally interviewed with a semi-structured questionnaire. A total of ten key informants were interviewed to identify the bottlenecks of the existing legal, policy, and institutional frameworks for adoption of the nature-based mitigation strategies to sea level rise and other climate change impacts on the Sundarbans Mangrove of Bangladesh. Based on respondents' perceptions, a mitigation strategy was developed. Content analysis was done to analyze the data.

Results

Bottlenecks in the institutional framework

Figure 3: Bottlenecks in the institutional framework

Bottlenecks in the legal and policy framework

Figure 4: Bottlenecks in the legal and policy framework

Nature-based mitigation strategies (based on respondents' perceptions)

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